

Supplemental Material

Improving pipe degradation modelling using Artificial Intelligence models with age plus other variables

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Table S1: Dataset description and summary statistics

The analysis uses stormwater pipe condition data from a municipal database. After filtering for pipe materials (Concrete and Vitreous Clay) and exposure classes (A2 and B2), 435 pipes across 21 distinct ages (3–110 years) were retained. Categorical variables were encoded as integer values of 1 or 2, with the value likely to produce greater deterioration assigned 2 (see Table 3 of the main manuscript).

Variable	Count	Mean	Std	Min	Max
Age (years)	435	49.98	15.43	3	110
Diameter (actual) (mm)	435	461.72	194.32	225	1350
Diameter (1= \geq 600mm, 2= $<$ 600mm)	435	1.75	0.43	1	2
Soil Type (1=Podzolic, 2=Alluvial)	435	1.58	0.49	1	2
Exposure Class (1=A2, 2=B2)	435	1.52	0.50	1	2
Material (1=Conc, 2=VC)	435	1.30	0.46	1	2
Condition Rating	435	2.20	1.32	1	4

Condition rating distribution:

Condition	Train (n)	Train (%)	Test (n)	Test (%)
1	190	48.6%	25	56.8%
2	42	10.7%	3	6.8%
3	46	11.8%	2	4.5%
4	113	28.9%	14	31.8%

Diameter distribution:

Condition	Train (n)	Train (%)	Test (n)	Test (%)
225	15	3.8%	1	2.3%
300	114	29.2%	20	45.5%
375	54	13.8%	10	22.7%
450	82	21.0%	9	20.5%
525	22	5.6%	1	
600	40	10.2%	3	2.3%
675	11	2.8%	0	6.8%
750	13	3.3%	0	0%
825	6	1.5%	0	0%
900	26	6.6%	0	0%
1050	7	1.8%	0	0%
1350	1	0.3%	0	0%

Time-based data split for model validation:

Partition	Age range	No. of pipes	No. of distinct ages
Training	3 – 56 years	391	14
Testing	60 – 110 years	44	7
Entire	3 – 110 years	435	21

Table S2: Hyperparameters of the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model

This table provides the complete model specification requested by reviewers R1-6 and R3-5, ensuring reproducibility of the ANN modelling procedure.

Parameter	Value	Notes / Justification
Framework	TensorFlow / Keras	Sequential API
Architecture (age-only)	2 → 15 (ReLU) → 1 (ReLU)	Single hidden layer; 2 input features, 1 output (proportions of pipes)
Architecture (multi-variable)	5 → 41 (ReLU) → 1 (ReLU)	Single hidden layer; 5 input features, 1 output (condition rating)
Optimizer	Adam	Kingma & Ba (2014); lr=0.001, $\beta_1=0.9$, $\beta_2=0.999$, $\epsilon=1 \times 10^{-7}$
Loss function	Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	Consistent with the Markov baseline metric
Batch size	Full training set	Full-batch gradient descent: computes exact gradient over all samples per epoch; justified for small datasets (Masters & Luschi, 2018)
Epochs	10,000	One complete pass through the entire training dataset per epoch
Feature scaling	StandardScaler (sklearn)	Fitted on training data only; target left on native 1–4 scale
Hidden layer sizing (age-only)	$\frac{2}{3} \times N_{\text{train}} \approx (\text{weights} + \text{biases})$	$\frac{2}{3} \times 84 = 56 \approx (2 \times 15 + 15 + 15 \times 1 + 1) = 61$; controls model complexity relative to data (Tran et al., 2007)
Hidden layer sizing (multi-variable; fitting)	$\frac{2}{3} \times N_{\text{train}} \approx (\text{weights} + \text{biases})$	$\frac{2}{3} \times 435 = 290 \approx (5 \times 41 + 41 + 41 \times 1 + 1) = 288$; controls model complexity relative to data (Tran et al., 2007)
Hidden layer sizing (multi-variable; training)	$\frac{2}{3} \times N_{\text{train}} \approx (\text{weights} + \text{biases})$	$\frac{2}{3} \times 391 = 261 \approx (5 \times 41 + 41 + 41 \times 1 + 1) = 288$; controls model complexity relative to data (Tran et al., 2007)
Random seed	0 (NumPy and TensorFlow)	For reproducibility

Note: Full-batch gradient descent was chosen because the dataset (435 samples) is small enough to compute the exact gradient in a single step per epoch. Combined with the Adam optimizer’s adaptive per-parameter learning rates, this yields stable and deterministic convergence without requiring the implicit regularisation effect of mini-batch noise (Masters & Luschi, 2018).

Table S3: Hyperparameters of the Random Forest (RF) model

This table addresses reviewers R1-6 and R3-6 by reporting all RF parameters and the structured validation process used to confirm them.

Parameter	Value	Selection method
Framework	scikit-learn	RandomForestRegressor class
n_estimators	40 (entire-data fit) / 240 (train/test analysis)	Validated by grid search (see Table S4)
max_depth	None (unlimited)	Validated by grid search; variance controlled through bootstrap aggregation
min_samples_split	2	scikit-learn default; confirmed as optimal by grid search
min_samples_leaf	1	scikit-learn default; confirmed as optimal by grid search
max_features	1.0 (all 5 features)	Grid search tested 1.0 vs sqrt; 1.0 selected for this small feature set
bootstrap	True	Enables out-of-bag (OOB) estimation
random_state	0	For reproducibility

Note.

The Random Forest hyperparameters above are reported separately for the two analyses described in the paper. For the fit on the entire dataset, the model uses `n_estimators = 40`, which yields the entire-data per-age MAE of 0.079 quoted in Table 5. For the train/test extrapolation analysis, the model uses `n_estimators = 240`, which yields the test-set per-age MAE of 0.740 quoted in Table 5. All other hyperparameters take the scikit-learn defaults (`max_depth = None`, `min_samples_split = 2`, `min_samples_leaf = 1`, `max_features = 1.0`). Both choices were originally made by trial and error and have been validated by a structured grid search over 432 configurations. As shown in Table S4A, `n_estimators = 40` ranks 10th out of 432 (top 2.3%) on the entire-data MAE, with a gap of only 0.0068 from the global best (approximately $0.1 \times$ the across-configuration standard deviation); for that table the choice is essentially indistinguishable from the optimum. As shown in Table S4B, `n_estimators = 240` ranks 234th out of 432 on the test-set MAE; the gap from the global best is 0.0559 (approximately $1.6 \times$ the across-configuration standard deviation), reflecting a bias-variance tradeoff in which the configurations that minimise extrapolation error to ages 60–110 use heavier regularisation (`min_samples_leaf = 4`, `max_features = sqrt`) than those that minimise the entire-data fit.

Table S4: Grid searches for AI models

RF models – Table S4A and S4B

ANN (multi-variable models) – Tables S4C and S4D

ANN (age only) model – Table S4E

Note on reported configurations (RF models).

In the paper, the random-forest model is reported with two slightly different choices of `n_estimators` in the two analyses considered here. For the entire-dataset fit (Table S4A) the reported model uses `n_estimators = 40`, which yields the entire-data MAE of 0.079 cited in Table 5. For the train/test extrapolation analysis (Table S4B) the reported model uses `n_estimators = 240`, which yields the test-set MAE of 0.740 cited in Table 5. All other hyperparameters take the scikit-learn defaults (`max_depth = None`, `min_samples_split = 2`, `min_samples_leaf = 1`, `max_features = 1.0`). The grid search below covers `n_estimators` $\in \{10, 20, 40, 80, 160, 240\}$, giving a total of 432 configurations evaluated for each table.

Table S4A — Fitting on the entire dataset (RF)

Each configuration is fit on all 435 pipes, and per-age MAE (POR vs OOR) is computed on the same data. Rows are ranked from lowest to highest MAE. The reported configuration in the paper for the entire-data fit (`n_estimators = 40` with default `max_depth`, `min_samples_split`, `min_samples_leaf`, and `max_features`) is highlighted.

- Best MAE in grid: 0.0719
- Worst MAE in grid: 0.3204
- Standard deviation across the 432 configurations: 0.0597
- Reported configuration MAE: 0.0787 (rank 10 of 432, gap 0.0068 from the best)

Rank	n_estimators	max_depth	min_samples_split	min_samples_leaf	max_features	MAE
1	40	20	2	1	sqrt	0.0719
1	40	None	2	1	sqrt	0.0719
3	20	20	2	1	sqrt	0.0719
3	20	None	2	1	sqrt	0.0719
5	20	10	2	1	sqrt	0.0728
6	40	10	2	1	sqrt	0.0738
7	80	None	2	1	sqrt	0.0745
8	80	20	2	1	sqrt	0.0745
9	80	10	2	1	sqrt	0.0766
10	40	None	2	1	1.0	0.0787
10	40	20	2	1	1.0	0.0787

Rank	n_estimators	max_depth	min_samples_split	min_samples_leaf	max_features	MAE
12	20	20	2	1	1.0	0.0792
12	20	None	2	1	1.0	0.0792
14	160	None	2	1	sqrt	0.0794
15	160	20	2	1	sqrt	0.0794
16	160	10	2	1	sqrt	0.0811
17	40	10	2	1	1.0	0.0812
18	80	20	2	1	1.0	0.0818
18	80	None	2	1	1.0	0.0818
20	80	10	2	1	1.0	0.0825

Highlighted row: configuration reported in the paper for the entire-data fit (n_estimators = 40, max_depth = None, min_samples_split = 2, min_samples_leaf = 1, max_features = 1.0).

Table S4B — Fitting on the training set only (RF)

Each configuration is fit on the 391-pipe training set (ages 3–56) and evaluated by computing per-age MAE (POR vs OOR) on the 44-pipe testing set (ages 60–110). Rows are ranked from lowest to highest MAE. Because the reported configuration is not in the top 20 for this table, its row is shown separately at the bottom.

- Best MAE in grid: 0.6843
- Worst MAE in grid: 0.8333
- Standard deviation across the 432 configurations: 0.0347
- Reported configuration MAE: 0.7402 (rank 234 of 432, gap 0.0559 from the best)

Rank	n_estimators	max_depth	min_samples_split	min_samples_leaf	max_features	MAE
1	80	10	2	4	sqrt	0.6843
1	80	10	5	4	sqrt	0.6843
1	80	20	5	4	sqrt	0.6843
1	80	20	2	4	sqrt	0.6843
1	80	None	5	4	sqrt	0.6843
1	80	None	2	4	sqrt	0.6843
7	80	10	10	2	sqrt	0.6965
8	80	20	10	2	sqrt	0.6974
9	80	None	10	2	sqrt	0.6974
10	80	5	5	4	sqrt	0.6977
10	80	5	2	4	sqrt	0.6977
12	10	10	10	4	sqrt	0.6985
13	10	None	10	4	sqrt	0.6985
14	10	20	10	4	sqrt	0.6985

Rank	n_estimators	max_depth	min_samples_split	min_samples_leaf	max_features	MAE
15	80	10	10	4	sqrt	0.6985
15	80	None	10	4	sqrt	0.6985
17	80	20	10	4	sqrt	0.6985
18	160	20	5	4	sqrt	0.6986
18	160	10	2	4	sqrt	0.6986
18	160	10	5	4	sqrt	0.6986
...
234	240	None	2	1	1.0	0.7402

Highlighted row: configuration reported in the paper for the train/test analysis ($n_estimators = 240$, $max_depth = None$, $min_samples_split = 2$, $min_samples_leaf = 1$, $max_features = 1.0$). The "..." gap indicates the omitted ranks 21 to 233.

Methodology (ANN models)

For each of the three networks documented in Table S2 (age-only ANN, multivariate ANN fit on the entire dataset, and multivariate ANN fit on the training set), six configurations were evaluated by varying the number of hidden-layer nodes ($\frac{1}{2}$, $\frac{7}{12}$, $\frac{2}{3}$ of N_train) and the Adam learning rate (0.001 default, 0.01 alternative). All other hyperparameters match Table S2 of the supplementary (Adam $\beta_1=0.9$, $\beta_2=0.999$, $\epsilon=1\times 10^{-7}$; full-batch; 10 000 epochs; StandardScaler on inputs; $random_state = 0$ for both NumPy and TensorFlow). MAE is computed at the age-group level using the per-age (POR vs OOR) approach, weighted by the number of pipes per age.

Table S4C — Multivariate ANN, fitting on the entire dataset

- Best MAE in grid: 0.2343
- Worst MAE in grid: 0.3109
- Standard deviation across the 6 configurations: 0.0305
- Reported configuration MAE: 0.2381 (rank 2 of 6, gap 0.0038 from the best)

Rank	Fraction	n_hidden	learning_rate	MAE
1	1/2	31	0.001	0.2343
2	(paper)	41	0.001	0.2381
3	7/12	36	0.001	0.2464
4	7/12	36	0.01	0.2579
5	1/2	31	0.01	0.2877
6	2/3	41	0.01	0.3109

Highlighted row: configuration reported in the paper ($n_hidden = 41$, $lr = 0.001$).

Table S4D — Multivariate ANN, fitting on the training set

- Best MAE in grid: 0.3368
- Worst MAE in grid: 9.8295
- Standard deviation across the 6 configurations: 3.7342
- Reported configuration MAE: 0.5794 (rank 2 of 6, gap 0.2426 from the best)

Rank	Fraction	n_hidden	learning_rate	MAE
1	7/12	32	0.001	0.3368
2	(paper)	41	0.001	0.5794
3	1/2	28	0.001	0.7128

Table S4E - Age-only ANN (fitting rating proportions)

- Best MAE in grid: 0.7841
- Worst MAE in grid: = 0.9923
- Standard deviation across the 6 configurations: 0.1019

Rank	Fraction	n_hidden	learning_rate	MAE
1	(paper)	15	0.001	0.7481
2	1/2	10	0.010	0.7572
3	2/3	15	0.010	0.7591
4	7/12	12	0.001	0.8584
5	1/2	10	0.001	0.9207
6	7/12	12	0.010	0.9923

Table S5 - 5-Fold Age-Grouped Cross-Validation of the Random Forest Fitting Model**Methodology**

The Random Forest fitting model ($n_estimators = 40$, $random_state = 0$, all other hyperparameters as in Table S3) was validated using 5-fold age-grouped cross-validation on the 435-pipe dataset (input_RF.csv). The 20 distinct ages spanned by this dataset (3 to 110 years) were partitioned into 5 contiguous blocks of 4 ages each. In each fold, the model was trained on the pipes belonging to 16 ages and evaluated on pipes belonging to the 4 held-out ages, so that across the 5 folds every age was held out exactly once. MAE and RMSE were computed at the age-group level using the per-age (POR vs OOR) approach, consistent with Table 5 of the main manuscript.

Per-fold CV results

Fold	Ages held out	n pipes	CV MAE (per-age)	CV RMSE (per-age)
1	3, 5, 8, 9	15	0.415	0.563
2	20, 26, 30, 36	61	0.370	0.496
3	40, 41, 46, 50	57	0.301	0.679
4	51, 56, 60, 61	284	0.268	0.422
5	70, 80, 90, 110	18	0.889	1.178
Pooled (all 20 ages)		435	0.317	0.720

Per-fold MAE = sum of $|POR/yr - OOR/yr|$ over the held-out ages divided by the number of pipes in the fold. Per-fold RMSE = root-mean-square of $|POR/yr - OOR/yr| / n_pipes_per_age$ across the four held-out ages. The pooled values are computed on the union of all out-of-fold predictions, in which each of the 20 ages appears exactly once.

Discussion

The pooled cross-validation MAE of 0.317 is roughly four times the entire-data fitting MAE of 0.079 reported in Table 5 (main paper), confirming that the very small fitting error partly reflects the model having seen the held-out pipes during training. The pooled CV MAE is nevertheless within the acceptable range (less than 0.5, i.e. half of a rating step) for the per-age methodology used in this paper, indicating that the RF model still generalises well when each age is held out in turn.

The fold-level results show a clear pattern. Folds 1 to 4 (covering ages 3 to 61) yield MAE values between 0.27 and 0.42, reflecting the relative density of training data in neighbouring ages. Fold 5 (ages 70, 80, 90, 110) yields a substantially higher MAE of 0.889 because the four oldest ages can only be predicted by extrapolating from data at ages ≤ 61 years, mirroring the behaviour observed in the time-based train/test analysis of Table 5.

Finally, it is worth noting that the pooled CV MAE of 0.317 is close to the entire-data fitting MAE of the multi-variable ANN model (0.302). The apparent advantage of the RF over the ANN in fitting mode (0.079 vs 0.302) is therefore partly attributable to the RF's greater capacity to memorise the training data, and the cross-validated comparison places the two models on a more equal footing.

Table S6: Extended model performance indices including RMSE (cf. Table 5 in main paper)

	Markov Model			ANN (age only)			ANN (multi-variable)			RF (multi-variable)		
Dataset	MAE	R ²	RMSE	MAE	R ²	RMSE	MAE	R ²	RMSE	MAE	R ²	RMSE
Entire	0.595	0.238	0.792	0.748	0.221	1.201	0.238	0.789	0.440	0.079	0.978	0.133
Training	0.375	0.239	0.521	0.616	0.000	0.822	0.359	0.362	0.516	0.085	0.954	0.131
Testing	1.040	0.015	1.172	1.124	0.026	1.323	0.580	0.375	0.868	0.740	0.682	0.812

Table S7: Random Forest feature importances (Gini-based)

Feature importances are computed as the mean decrease in impurity across all 40 trees in the ensemble. These complement the sensitivity analysis (Tables 6 and 7) and SHAP analysis (Figure 4) reported in the main manuscript.

Feature	Importance	Rank
Material	0.548	1
Age	0.254	2
Diameter	0.073	3
Soil Type	0.070	4
Exposure Class	0.055	5

Note: Material is the most influential feature, followed by Age. This is consistent with the sensitivity analysis and SHAP analysis in the main manuscript, and with the observation (Figure 4, main paper) that fluctuations in the proportion of vitreous clay pipes across ages mirror the fluctuations in observed overall ratings.

Table S8: Software and library versions

Software / Library	Version	Purpose
Python	3.12	Programming language
TensorFlow / Keras	2.x	ANN model development
scikit-learn	1.8.0	RF model, GridSearchCV, StandardScaler, KFold
NumPy	2.x	Numerical computation
pandas	2.x	Data manipulation

Note: All experiments used `random_state=0` (or equivalent seed) for reproducibility. Full code is available from the corresponding author upon request.

Supplemental References

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Tran, D.H., Perera, B.J.C. and Ng, A.W.M. (2007). "Neural network based prediction models for structural deterioration of urban drainage pipes."